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The 62nd TEFLIN International Conference 2015
ISBN: 978-602-294-066-1

**ADVERTISEMENTS AS AUTHENTIC MULTIMODAL TEXTS:
BRIDGING 21ST CENTURY SKILLS AND ENGLISH SKILLS TEACHING
PRACTICE DIVIDE**

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Abstract: The essence of 21st century learning, with its newly important set of skills, is the emphasis on what students can do with knowledge they gain, rather than what units of knowledge they have. This implies that our students cannot do anything without learning the knowledge, thus they should learn about skills and content altogether and at the same time. This challenges us, EFL teachers, to effectively and selectively teach both English skills and 21st century skills to the students. This paper explores the possibilities of intertwining the teaching of critical, communication, and information literacy skills as 21st century skills with English literacy skills for EFL university students. Advertisements are exploited in the literacy practice activities as authentic multimodal materials to bridge the gap possibly resulted by the integration of critical, information and communication literacy skills into literacy activities, since these forms of information are authentic multimodal texts which are ubiquitous and never free from bias and power. The project-based activities with guided literacy instruction are designed to: elicit students' critical thinking skills in analyzing the content of advertisements; encourage students' communication skills by giving comments on the advertisements' situational purposes; and empower students' information literacy skills by choosing and producing their own advertisements as form of communication. Performance-based assessment is implemented to assist students when completing and performing their project-based assignment.

Keywords: literacy skills, multimodal, instruction, assessment

The goal of 21st century is to empower the countries to become knowledge-based nation (Association for Career and Technical Education, et.al, 2010). To achieve

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this goal, the learning in 21st century is known as the century of the mind, characterized by information access and utilization, knowledge development, and lifelong learning. This goal is to overcome the skills shortage happens in worldwide, as reported by Association for Career and Technical Education, et.al (2010:9). Skills shortage in 21st century, a “mismatch between worker’s qualification and the specific skill sets and combinations of skills employers want” (Association for Career and Technical Education, et.al, 2010), is resulted from rapid growth of technology. Although technology has created a new generation of digital natives, they still lack skills highly required by the employers to effectively make benefits of technology for this knowledge-based needs. The skills, such as critical thinking, communication, and information literacy, are not new, yet are newly important skills in the 21st century (Silva, 2009; Noss, 2012), signals that students in 21st century are now highly demanded to master these newly important set of skills.

The essence of 21st century learning is the emphasis on what students can do with knowledge they gain, rather than what units of knowledge they have. This implies that students cannot do anything without learning the knowledge, thus they should learn about skills and content altogether and at the same time. To overcome the problem of skills shortage that has challenged our nation, teachers of English should teach both English skills and 21st century skills to the students.

WHY TEACHING 21ST CENTURY SKILLS?

The teaching of EFL in 21st century must be centered on preparing students to be excellent in their academic and career life, thus it requires both teaching of content and skills that students need. To achieve this, EFL teaching practice in 21st century must be expanded into not only mastering English skills required to communicate with global citizen, but also mastering 21st century learning skills to overcome the skills

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shortage happens worldwide. In other words, knowledge and content mastery are not enough to be successful in 21st century. Our students need 21st century skills to enable them to apply their already possessed knowledge and content. For example, to become a proficient reader, students should be able to bring their background knowledge, both linguistic devices and information content, to any texts that they read. They need specific sets of skills to comprehend and make the best use of the texts they read – such as critically analyze the texts, differentiate information, use technology to reproduce the text, and choose appropriate media to share its content.

21ST CENTURY SKILLS AND ENGLISH SKILLS TEACHING

PRACTICE DIVIDE

Several research findings revealed that there is a gap between EFL skills and 21st century skills teaching practices, indicated by teachers' hesitation in integrating those practices since the integration would pose greater difficulty to the students, when compared to their L1 counterparts, which are caused by the differences of their sociocultural and linguistic socialization practices (Johnston, 2014; Sholihah, 2012; Ihmeideh et. al, 2010; Sidek, 2010). However, if we desire our English teaching practice to be successful for our students, then we have to realize that a successful English education can no longer be achieved by having them merely memorize a set of facts, strategies, and ways of communicating in English during their English education each year. Instead, we must teach English in ways that also help our students learn how to learn, so that they can use English in new situations and manage the demands of changing information, technologies, jobs, and social conditions. We cannot expect our students to speak English without teaching them communication skills; to be proficient in comprehending English texts without teaching them critical thinking skills; and to be fluent writer in creating English texts without teaching them information literacy skills.

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Consequently, we must integrate the teaching of 21st century learning skills with the English skills teaching practice (Luk & Lin, 2015; Gilfert, 2011).

**BRIDGING THE DIVIDE: USING ADVERTISEMENTS AS MULTIMODAL
TEXTS**

Advertisements are designed to persuade us, the consumers, to make purchase for the advertised products. Advertisements entrench information, wrapped persuasively with eye-and-ear-catching audio-visual images and words to market the products. Contemporary advertisements are ubiquitous and are communicated intensively through television, movies, magazines, and the internet. One of the easiest media and the most frequently accessed media, where advertisements appear almost anytime, is YouTube. YouTube has successfully served its role as almost limitless source of multimodal texts that is easily accessed by anyone, including digital immigrant teachers and students. Advertisements are multimodal texts that centralize the juxtaposition of graphics, language, images, sounds, and other modes to carry its meaning. As multimodal texts, advertisements are filled with bias and power (Assaf & Adony, 2010) since these texts use video, audio, and print representation to carry its message to the society. The integration of multiple modes in advertisements creates complex and layered combination of messages that should be cracked by the reader or viewer to comprehend its real meaning. Considering its ubiquitous nature, learning to read advertisements becomes “naturalized” and must be considered as a part of our daily lives and routines. Scholars argue that learning to read advertisements will help students develop skills of English, build their empathy, learn collaboratively, and focus on several things at once (Serafini, 2012a; 2012b; Assaf & Adony, 2010; Kress & van Leeuwen, 2006). Since advertisements are multimodal texts, they include various pathways to read. Therefore, in the context of English teaching, our students must

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be taught to engage themselves in meaning-making processes to comprehend advertisements. Teaching English advertisement texts, therefore, offers a rich opportunity to help students critically evaluate and analyze the messages it brings to the society that are relevant in their lives.

ACTIVITIES TO INTEGRATE 21ST CENTURY SKILLS AND ENGLISH SKILLS TEACHING PRACTICE

Project-based learning is highly recommended to be used in teaching integrated 21st century learning skills and English skills to EFL students (Boss & Krauss, 2007). Project-based learning makes possible for the students to learn by engaging in real-world projects. They may choose their own learning pathways, including choose kinds of technology they need to help them complete the project. The activities are therefore shifting from merely following teacher's lead, to discussing, debating and exchanging ideas to complete the project.

To be successfully used, the project should be designed and structured to maximize English language, content and real-life 21st century learning skills, and those require a combination of teacher guidance and feedback and student engagement. Later, this project should be developed with elaborated tasks with some degree of challenge to promote students' skills, and focused on real-world subject matter to build students' interest in learning English skills and 21st century skills. The project requires students-to-students collaboration, as well as their autonomy and independence during completing their group project, and requires students-to-teacher to guide them complete the project. Since the project is process and product oriented, it should accommodate a purposeful and explicit focus on form and other aspects of English, such as highlighting the grammatical rules of English and its vocabularies used as communicative means in the advertisement as the project outcome.

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Activities in Table 1 are project-based activities with guided literacy instruction, designed to expose EFL students to the communicative use of English found in authentic English advertisements. These project-based activities can be done in either English skills subjects or content subjects. Levels of students for these activities are intermediate to advance, since they are assumed to have adequate English knowledge needed to communicate a project. The activities are designed to be conducted in two weeks, in order to maximize the integrated teaching of English skills and 21st century skills.

While exposing students to the communicative use of English, students can be guided to elicit their critical thinking skills during by analyzing the content of advertisements; encourage their communication skills by giving comments on the advertisements' situational purposes, and; empower their information literacy skills by choosing and producing their own advertisements as form of communication. Before following the activities, teachers of EFL are suggested to apply these steps:

- Step 1* : teacher communicates with the students to discuss about the theme of their project.
- Step 2* : teacher with students determine the outcome of the project, covers the deadline for project presentation, the form of presentation, the media to share the project, and the format of the project (whether it is audio-based, printed-based, or audiovisual-based advertisements).
- Step 3* : teacher with students structure their timeline for project consultation and their target for every consultation session.
- Step 4* : students discuss the advertisements content of their project with teacher based on the set timeline.
- Step 5* : students discuss the use of English as a means of communication for their

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project with the teacher.

Step 6 : students give mock presentation for their final draft project before the teacher.

Step 7 : teacher gives feedback on their mock presentation. The feedback is meant to perfect their project for their final presentation.

Step 8 : students present their final product as their project before the class.

Table 1. Integrated Activities for English Skills and 21st Century Learning Skills

Week 1		
Skills	:	Viewing and speaking
Level	:	Intermediate to advance
Theme	:	Favorite food and beverages
Material	:	Advertisements of McDonald's version Proud Papa (downloaded from https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=5ZdALTZ6aA8)
Time allotted	:	90 minutes
Method	:	Project-based learning
Assessment	:	Performance-based assessment
Learning Objectives	:	Students give comments about appropriateness or inappropriateness of advertisements
Learning Outcomes	:	Oral presentation about appropriateness or inappropriateness of advertisements to target audience
Instructions for Activities	:	In group, view the sample advertisements, and do the following: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Identify the product being advertised 2. Identify the target audiences or consumers for the product 3. Decide whether the ways of communicating the product being advertised is appropriate for the target audiences or

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Instructions for project homework	:	Advertisements of favorite food and beverages. <i>Option A:</i> in group, create your own advertisement. Use multiple modes in creating the advertisement. The following are the questions to guide you create your advertisement.
Week 2		
Skills	:	Speaking and writing
Level	:	Intermediate to advance
Theme	:	Favorite food and beverages
Material	:	Advertisements of McDonald's version Proud Papa (downloaded from https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=5ZdALTZ6aA8)
Time allotted	:	90 minutes
Method	:	Project-based learning
Assessment	:	Performance-based assessment
Learning Objectives	:	1. Students advertise favorite food and beverages by using appropriate media and modes 2. Students compare and contrast advertisements
Learning Outcomes	:	1. Advertisements of favorite food and beverages as group project 2. Oral presentation about similarities and differences of the sample advertisement and students' advertisements
Instructions for activities	:	Students should: 1. advertise their project for the intended target consumer clearly and comprehensibly through speaking and writing 2. operate technology in presenting their project and for providing better viewing experience for the audience 3. <u>choose appropriate media to advertise their project</u>

ASSESSING STUDENTS’ ENGLISH SKILLS AND 21ST CENTURY SKILLS PERFORMANCE

Performance-based assessment, when conducted to assess students’ performance in completing the projects, allows teachers to gather information about what students can do with their knowledge that is gained through learning. This assessment provides information for teachers about how students think, collaborate, and try to complete the project given, and how to communicate their project using English. Table 2 displays indicators for 21st century skills, in which English skills performance of EFL students are integrated within it.

Table 2. Indicators for Students’ Performance

Critical Thinking	Identify product and target audience for sample advertisement
	Provide reasons for appropriateness/ inappropriateness use of linguistics devices and advertisement features of sample advertisement
	Show advertisement features and linguistic devices in sample advertisement to support their argument
Communication	Advertise their project for target consumer clearly and comprehensibly through speaking and writing
	Operate technology in presenting project and for providing better viewing experience for audience
	Use multiple modes in creating / reconstructing sample advertisement for project
Information Literacy	Choose appropriate media to advertise project
	Compare and contrast the sample advertisement and project for audience’s information
	Give clear information on the excellence of their product to audience and media they choose to advertise product

During their performance when presenting the project, teachers can observe their strengths and weaknesses in performing English skills and 21st century skills and

later can use that information to design classroom instruction accordingly. Teachers can use rubric for assessing students' performance in Table 3. Rubric for assessing students' performance are explained in Table 3.

Table 3. Assessment Rubric for Student' Performance

Critical Thinking			
Advanced	Proficient	Developing	Beginning
1	2	3	4
Analyze sample advertisements by showing each of the following indicators	Analyze sample advertisements by showing two of the following indicators	Analyze sample advertisements by showing at least one of the following indicators.	Student is beginning to identify linguistics devices and features of sample advertisements yet cannot provide reasons for appropriateness / inappropriateness use of linguistics devices and advertisements features
Communication			
Communicate the project by showing each of the indicators.	Communicate the project by showing two of the indicators.	Communicate the project by showing one of the indicators.	Student is beginning to operate technology in order to advertise their project yet without clear and comprehensible presentation
Information Literacy			
Inform audience about project by showing each of the indicators.	Inform audience about project by showing each of the indicators.	Inform audience about project by showing each of the indicators.	Student is beginning to choose technology to advertise project with little information on the excellence of product compared to the product in sample advertisement.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

This century has challenged us, teachers of EFL, to reshape our teaching and learning practice in EFL classrooms. EFL teaching and learning practice must meet

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economic, workforce and civil needs that are later faced by our students, in order to prepare them to succeed in their life. Integrating the teaching of English skills with the teaching of 21st century skills, which is bridged by using advertisements as multimodal texts, can become one of the many ways of reshaping our teaching and learning practice. Only by reshaping the assignment, activities, learning outcomes and assessments can we prepare our students to enter the globally competitive world.

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